

METHODS AND PROBLEMS OF TRANSLATING ENGLISH NEWSPAPER
TEXTS INTO UZBEK

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Abstract: This article analyses the effective use of translation transformation methods that can be used in the translation of English newspaper texts into Uzbek, as well as their peculiarities and problems. In addition, linguists spoke about their scientific research in the translation of newspaper texts. Also, instructions are given to translators for successful translation of English newspaper texts.

Keywords: Grammatical transformation, Lexical transformation, Syntactic transformations, Transliteration, copying, substitution, replacement of clauses, substitution, omission, modulation

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INTRODUCTION

Stylistics is a special branch of linguistics that studies styles and stylistic resources. Styles are varieties of language, due to differences in the areas of communication and the main functions of the language [1]. Publicistic style occupies a special place in the system of styles of the literary language, since in many cases it must process texts created within other styles. The journalistic style as a whole is characterized by a special emotionality, "passion, evaluativeness (in terms of socio-political significance)", sharpness of expression, polemicalness.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Journalism not only reflects everyday life, but also forms public opinion. Publicism is based on the principles of "social and evaluative use of linguistic means". The language of journalism combines in formativeness, logicity and "mandatory emotionality, evaluativeness, the unity of such opposing linguistic tendencies as an orientation towards standardization of speech, the use of speech standards (speech clichés), on the one hand, and the desire for expression, for the revitalization of speech, on the other". In formativeness ("informative and communicative function") of the language of journalism is manifested in the orientation to speech standards (cliches). For example, to be in the forefront, to report, to make an important contribution, to lead the standings, to bring to life, to meet difficulties, etc. Publicistic style is an open system that includes elements of other styles.

Different translation options can be used in the translation process of newspaper style texts. It should be noted that the study of translation methods was

carried out by many linguists, for example, A. D. Schweitzer, L. S. Barkhudarov, L. K. Latvishev, R. K. Minyar-Beloruchev, V. N. Komissarov, I. Retsker, V. G. Gak and others [Schweitzer, 2000; Barkhudarov, 1975, Minyar-Beloruchev, 1969; Komissarov, 1990; Retsker, 1974; Gak, 2003]. They give their own definition of the term "translational transformations". One of the founders of the definition is L. S. Barkhudarov. According to this definition, translation transformations are permutations of original text elements, cross-linguistic transformations, restatement or paraphrasing operations to achieve a translation equivalent [Barkhudarov, 1975, p. 45].

Translation transformations can be classified as grammatical, lexical and syntactic. Grammar transformation includes subtraction, substitution, replacement and addition of sentences. Lexical transformations include methods such as transcription, transliteration, calking, concretization, summarization of sentences, and substitution. Syntactic transformations include separating and combining sentences, syntactic assimilation, compensation, antonymic translation, descriptive translation, synonymous substitutions and other types of substitutions [Levitskaya, 1963, p. 103].

All types of grammatical transformations are used in the translation of newspaper texts. News articles and reports are the most dry, formal and concise style. Such articles can be translated more precisely by using syntactic reconstruction of sentences, lexical adaptations and structural substitutions. Sentence reconstruction is required to translate short messages [Latishev, 1983, p. 34].

The leading methods of translating non-equivalent vocabulary are transcription, transliteration and calking. Translators often use a mixture of transcription and transliteration with their subsequent explanations, that is, descriptive translation. Transcription is the transfer of the source language word through the translation language alphabet, taking into account the pronunciation in that language.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Transliteration means the transfer of the graphic form of the word source language using the translation language. For example:

"A weak rouble and rampant inflation that have been exacerbated by western sanctions over Ukraine has prompted General Motors to announce a huge retrenchment in Russia". (Times, 19/03/2015)

"Ukrainadagi voqealar munosabati bilan Rossiyaga qarshi G'arb sanksiyalari tufayli kuchaygan zaif rubl va qochib ketgan inflyatsiya Jeneral Motorsni Rossiyada tejamkorlik choralari e'lon qilishga undadi".

An example of transliteration in this sentence is the lexeme "General Motors".

Another method of translation is calking, in which the source language lexical unit is corrected by replacing the constituent elements with the corresponding target language lexical units. With the help of calking, a new word or set of phrases is formed in the language being studied. There are many examples of calking. For example:

"The official opening of the tallest skyscraper in Europe was timed to coincide with the start of the Olympic Games in London". (Guardian, 14/05/2013).

"Yevropadagi eng baland osmono'par binoning rasmiy ochilishi Londondagi Olimpiya o'yinlari boshlanishiga to'g'ri keldi".

The most common type of translation conversion is substitution. Substitutions, in turn, are divided into substitutions of word forms when the number of the noun changes in the translation. For example:

"Vitamin pills cannot replace fruit and vegetables - in fact, taking too many supplements may increase the risk of cancer, an expert has warned. (Times, 21/04/2015)

"Mutaxassislar vitaminlar meva va sabzavotlarning o'rnini bosa olmaydi va oziqaviy qo'shimchalarni haddan tashqari iste'mol qilish saraton xavfini oshirishi haqida ogohlantirmoqda".

Several methods have been used to translate this sentence. In the original sentence, the word "vitamin" is singular, "pills" is omitted, and therefore it becomes plural in the translated language. Here we also observe the replacement of parts of speech when "taking" is translated as "iste'mol" according to the nominative feature of the Uzbek language. The verb is nominalized. Here we see the addition when "the risk of cancer" is translated as "saraton xavfini oshirish" because this phrase is stable and easier for an Uzbek reader to understand.

The next type of substitution is the substitution of parts of speech. It is very common to replace an adjective with a noun, especially an adjective derived from a geographical name. For example:

"Tsipras, the Greek prime minister, made his official visit to Germany yesterday". (The Times, 24.03.2015)

"Kecha Gretsiya Bosh vaziri Aleksis Tsipras Germaniyaga rasmiy tashrif bilan keldi".

Changing adjectives to adverbs, nouns to verbs, adverbs to adjectives, etc. - all this is present in the translation of newspaper texts. For example:

"An attempted crime by suicide bomber was registered in New-York". (Washington Times, 30/04/2014)

"Nyu-Yorkda o'z joniga qasd qilishga urinish haqida xabar berildi".

In this sentence, the adjective "attempted" is translated as a verb, as there is no corresponding equivalent.

As in other functional styles of newspaper-journalistic style, there is often a change of clauses. For example:

"Two hostages, one American and one Italian, held by al-Qaeda were killed in a US drone strike". (Times, 26/04/2015)

"AQSh dron hujumi "Al-Qoida" tomonidan garovga olingan amerikalik va italiyaliklarni o'ldirdi".

When translating this sentence, it was necessary to replace the members of the sentence due to the restructuring of the syntactic structure.

The next very common transformation is replacement. The English language is characterized by a strict word order, while the Uzbek language is freer. Therefore, translators often use the replacement technique. For example:

"New law in education was adopted in Russia yesterday". (Guardian, 02.02.2014)

"Kecha Rossiyada ta'lim sohasida yangi qonun qabul qilindi".

In this example, "yesterday" is at the end of the sentence in the source language, and at the beginning of the sentence in the translated language, because informational messages in Uzbek begin with the suffix of time and place, followed by other members of the sentence.

Consider the following example:

"Israel's prime minister accused the United States yesterday of negotiating a nuclear deal that was a "danger to humanity". (Times, 30/03/2015)

"Kecha Isroil Bosh vaziri Qo'shma Shtatlarni butun insoniyatni xavf ostiga qo'yadigan yadroviy dastur shartlarini muhokama qilishda aybladi".

This is another example of sentence replacement, but there are other ways. Replacing the noun "danger" with a verb, the word "shartlar" was added. Adverbs are used to clarify the meaning of a word. This is due to differences in sentence structure. Since the English language is more concise, the Uzbek language requires a detailed expression of the idea. For example,

"There is regulatory requirement in certain industries such as construction and transport, that employers provide a safe working environment". (Guardian, 12/17/2014)

"Qurilish va transport kabi ba'zi sohalar ish beruvchilar uchun xavfsiz ish muhitini ta'minlash uchun qonuniy talabga ega".

The word "field" is added to this sentence because it's a cliché that's stuck.

Unlike addition, there is also omission. This method is used to avoid overexposure. In the sentence, elements that do not perform any semantic function are omitted. In the translation into Uzbek, the article and auxiliary verbs are omitted due to the objective differences between the languages. For example:

"Newspapers continue to occupy an important role in society".

"Gazetalar jamiyatda hali muhim rol o'ynashda davom etmoqda."

In the above sentence, "continue" is omitted, it is covered by the synonym word "hali".

When concretization is used, a word with a broad meaning in English is translated into Uzbek with a word with a narrow meaning. Many linguists have repeatedly emphasized that the vocabulary of the Uzbek language is more unique than the vocabulary of the English language. For example:

"The victory in the UEFA Champions League went to the team «Real Madrid» at the additional time". (Guardian, 15/05/2015)

"Real Madrid" qo'shimcha bo'limlardan so'ng UEFA Chempionlar ligasini qo'lga kiritdi".

English verbs like "go", "be", "come" etc. have many meanings and require precision in translation. As in this sentence, went is translated as "yutdi" because this verb is more often combined with "g'alaba" nouns.

The next method of translation is modulation or semantic development. At the same time, the translator replaces the source language word with a translation language word with a rethought meaning. For example:

"A politician must have a twisted conspiratorial mindset to even attempt to deny the obvious". (Guardian, 19.01.2015)

"Siyosatchi hatto aniq narsalarni inkor etishga urinish uchun fitnachi fikrga ega bo'lishi kerak."

In this example, the adjective "conspiratorial" is modulated because "thinking" cannot be "conspiratorial", so this semantic development is appropriate here.

The opposite phenomenon of concretization is generalization, that is, the transfer of a narrow concept to a broader concept. But translators from English to Uzbek use this method less often. For example,

"Pesticides temporarily banned because of fears that they kill honeybees could also damage populations of bumble bees, butterflies and moths, scientists claim." (Times, 04/09/2015).

"Olimlar asalarilar va boshqa hasharotlar populyatsiyasini yo'q qilishdan qo'rqib, pestitsidlardan foydalanishni vaqtincha to'xtatishni talab qilmoqdalar."

This generalization is appropriate, because for an Uzbek reader, listing all the names of insects is unnecessary information. But you can not abuse this technique.

Sentences are not always translated using different grammatical transformations. Sometimes the sentence structure is completely preserved in the language being translated. This phenomenon is called syntactic assimilation. For example, the following sentence retains the same structure as its English version:

"The Soviet government has authorised the Soviet Ambassador in the United States, V. N. Zarubin, to take part in these discussions". (Guardian, 07.05.2015)

"Sovet hukumati AQShdagi elchisi V. N. Zarubinga munozaralarda ishtirok etish huquqini berdi".

Another example:

"More than 1,900 people have been killed across four countries after a devastating 7.9 magnitude earthquake struck Nepal yesterday, collapsing buildings onto victims and triggering deadly avalanches on Mount Everest." (The Times, 25/04/2015)

"Kecha Nepalda sodir bo'lgan 7,9 magnitudali dahshatli zilzila to'rtta davlatdan 1900 dan ortiq kishining umriga zomin bo'ldi. U ko'plab binolarni vayron qildi va Everest tog'ida qor ko'chkisini keltirib chiqardi."

In the first sentence the passive construction is translated into an active construction. In the Uzbek language, the active voice is preferred over the passive voice. It is also used in translation because it is difficult to divide the sentence. The gerund is used very often in English. And in this sentence, "collapsing" and "triggering" are translated into Uzbek as verbs.

Splitting and combining sentences is related to the fact that Uzbek becomes difficult to understand when translating from English, so it is appropriate to use sentence splitting. On the contrary, if the idea of the first one develops in the second sentence, then the sentences should be combined. Let's take an example of sentence splitting:

"Overseeing the largest military parade since the collapse of the Soviet Union, Vladimir Putin yesterday took a swipe at America, accusing the Kremlin's Second World War ally turned Cold War rival of undermining international co-operation." (The Times, 5/10/2015)

"Kecha Sovet Ittifoqi parchalanganidan keyingi eng yirik harbiy paradda Vladimir Putin Amerikani tanqid qildi. U Kremlning Ikkinchi Jahon urushidagi ittifoqchisini Sovuq urushni xalqaro hamkorlikka putur yetkazganlikda aybladi."

In this example, sentence division was used, because short sentences are characteristic of the Uzbek newspaper-journalistic style, so the effect of redundancy was avoided.

A translator may also use an antonymic translation. In this case, the idea about the lexical unit of the source language is expressed through the opposite concept in the translation language with a change in its content. This technique is often used to add expressiveness to a sentence when translating from English to Uzbek. For example:

"The foreign secretary has warned that multinational companies will stop investing in India if the country fails to abolish its tax regime". (Times, 03/13/2015)

"Tashqi ishlar vaziri, agar mamlakat soliq rejimini bekor qilmasa, transmilliy kompaniyalar Hindistonga sarmoya kiritishda davom etmasligi haqida ogohlantirdi".

The replacement of "will" with "etmaslik" was caused by the use of an overt negation, and the use of the verb "davom et" instead of the verb "stop" is a hidden negation, that is, an antonym translation was used.

CONCLUSION

Thus, there are many ways to translate newspaper texts. But they must be used correctly. Greater equivalence can be achieved when translating socio-political articles, as generally accepted terms are used. Difficulties always arise due to colloquial vocabulary, specific speeches of politicians, slang and translation of compound words. A translator must be skilled enough to translate such aspects of newspaper style.

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